

A Comparative Study of Behavioural Pattern in Children of 5-15 Years of Age in Single Child Vs Child with Siblings

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Abstract:-

Background: Behavior can be defined as the way in which an individual behaves or acts towards others especially on a particular occasion. Behavior is the mirror which reflects one's true self. The patterns of behavior displayed by children are important indications of their growth and development.

Objective: to compare the behaviour of a single child and sibling child between the age group 5-15 years of age.

Methodology: Children aged 5-15 years attending OPD in Paediatrics Department of Hi-Tech MCH, Bhubaneswar from September 2019 to October 2021 were included. A Child Behavior Checklist was used to assess the behavioral quality of the children. It is a questionnaire containing 50 items. Each item scores 0, 1 and 2 respectively for Not True, Sometimes True and Very True. The maximum possible score was 100 and the total score was categorized as Good behaviour pattern (score 0 - 54), Average behaviour pattern (score 55 - 77) and Poor behaviour pattern (score 78 - 100). Depending upon the score, the children were categorized into good, average, poor behavior pattern. Data was entered into MS Excel, tabulated and analyzed using appropriate statistical tests.

Results: Out of total 220 children (110- single child, 110 child with sibling) most of the Single child, 79(71.8%) had average behaviour pattern as compared to Child with siblings, whose maximum children 97(88%) had good behaviour pattern.

Conclusion: Its better to have atleast 2 children in a family than a single child as siblings help a lot in modifying and shaping the behaviour pattern of a child.

Keywords: single child, siblings, parents, behaviour, modified behaviour checklist.

I. INTRODUCTION

"If children live with acceptance & friendship, they learn to find love in the world".

The Indian population was around 121 crores by the year 2011 census, there was a implementation of a two-child family program for promotion of family planning, which began in earnest in 2020 and resulted in a decrease in the population growth rate from 2.0% in 2001 to 1.6% in 2011[15th Indian census, 2011].^[1]

Family planning has been proclaimed as a fundamental state policy and this is necessary for the social and economic development. Two-child couples now account for 45.6% of the total married population[<http://main.mohfw.gov.in>].^[2]

The quality of child behavior will inevitably change over time and even on a daily or hourly basis. It is important to recognize that it is completely normal and can be a result of a wide range of events and situations[Basten et al. 2016]^[3]

Throughout the World around 13-14% school children have behavioral problem. A cross sectional study was conducted and behavioral problems of these children were estimated by using the self-reported under a version of the strengths and difficulties questionnaires. [World statistics 2018]^[4]

Many researchers have come across many children with altered behavioral pattern. It was found that the children were very depressed and had the feeling of separation, loneliness, not interested to go to school. So the researchers decided to choose to compare the behavioral quality of a single child and sibling child. [Kang, J. H. 2009]^[5]

The behavioral pattern of a child can be affected by many factors such as physical illness, change in school environment, family circle, peer pressure, socioeconomic status. It is the sole duty of parents identify significant changes and deal with them with patience. [Basten, M., 2016]^[3]

The growing years of a child are very important and perhaps the most difficult time for a family. It is during

these years that a child comes to terms with various concepts of life. [Baydar 1997]^[6]

The environment that a child is raised place a big part in their personal development. Younger children are usually very different from their older siblings. They tend to be more social and funny as they don't have as much responsibility like the elder ones. They experience good social relationships . [Brody 2011]^[7]

Only children have traits similar to older children but need to be given plenty of opportunities to socialize with children at their own age. Although only children often mature beyond their age, they should not be overburdened with expectations and responsibilities because they are still immature. [Gazi F. Begum, J. Blacher, 2011]^[8]

Only children have poorer interpersonal skills and they have to deal with loneliness and intrusion. [I. Bischooff, D. Tingstrom.(1991)]^[9]

Siblings of disabled children have been found to feel that their mothers were more partial to their disabled siblings, than without disabled children. They experience more stress and have a higher risk of developing behavioral problems [M. Allison, M. Campbell (2015)]^[10]

II. OBJECTIVE

To compare the behavioral quality of a single child and sibling child between 5-15 years of age.

III. METHODS

This study was a comparative type of descriptive study conducted on children 5-15 years of age visiting Pediatric Out Patient Department of Hi-Tech Medical College and Hospital from Sep 2019 to Oct 2021.

A. Inclusion Criteria:

- Children of age 5-15 years who were cooperating to participate in this study.
- Single child of the family.
- Child with one or more siblings in the family.
- Parents giving consent for the study.

B. Exclusion Criteria:

- Chronically ill children.
- Mentally retarded children.
- Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder.
- Child who lost his/her sibling recently.
- Children who were not willing to participate.
- Parents not giving consent for the study.

Before conducting the study, approval was taken from the Institutional Ethics committee (IEC) for human research of Hi-Tech medical college and hospital, Bhubaneswar.

During the study, consents were taken from the parents or guardians of the children under study and the confidentiality in relation to their information was assured to the respondents and was strictly maintained. They were also informed about the inconveniences associated with the study as a period of approximately 60 to 90 minutes would be needed to complete the schedule and perform the physical examination of the children.

This study was held at the Out-Patient Department of Paediatrics at Hi-Tech Medical College and Hospital. All children between 5-15 years of age satisfying the Inclusion Criteria were included in this study. A Child Behaviour checklist was used to determine the behavioural quality of the children. It is a questionnaire containing 50 items. Each item scores 0, 1, and 2 respectively for *Not True*, *Sometimes True and Very True*. The maximum possible score is 100 and the total score was categorized as –

<u>Category</u>	<u>Score</u>
➤ Good behaviour	: 0 - 54
➤ Average behaviour	: 55 - 77
➤ Poor behaviour	:78 - 100.

IV. QUESTIONNAIRE

No.	ITEM	Not True	Sometimes True	Very True
1.	Acting very immature for his/her age			
2.	Does a lot of arguments			
3.	Fails to finish the task recently started			
4.	Enjoys very little			
5.	Passing Bowel outside toilet			
6.	Bragging, Boasting			
7.	Can't concentrate, inattentive			
8.	Obsessed about certain things			
9.	Restless or hyperactive			
10.	Too much dependent on adults			
11.	Feeling very lonely			
12.	Seems very confused			
13.	Often cries a lot			
14.	Very cruel towards animals			
15.	Daydreaming, always lost in thoughts			
16.	Always attention-seeking			
17.	Destructive behavior towards own house belongings			
18.	Destroys own belongings			
19.	Doesnot obey parents at home			
20.	Disobedient to teachers at school			
21.	Very fussy while eating			
22.	Doesn't play with other kids			
23.	Doesn't feel guilty of mistakes			
24.	Easily becomes jealous			
25.	Disobedient to rules at home, school			
26.	Fearful at the time of going to school			
27.	Fearful of doing something bad			
28.	Always tries to be perfect			
29.	Feels no one loves him/her			
30.	Feels worthless or inferior to others			
31.	Often gets hurt and accident-prone			
32.	Fights with others over small things			
33.	Gets teased most often			
34.	Plays with troublesome children			
35.	Hears imaginative sounds			
36.	Impulsive towards acts			
37.	Likes to be alone than with others			
38.	Often lies or cheats others			
39.	Often seen biting fingernails			
40.	Feels nervous or tensed			
41.	Nervous movement or twitching			
42.	Suffers from nightmares			
43.	Not liked by other kids			
44.	Constipated and bowel retenting behavior			
45.	Often feels fearful or anxious			
46.	Feels lightheaded or dizzy			
47.	Often feels too guilty			
48.	Does overeating very often			
49.	Feels overtired with less work			
50.	Found to be overweight			

Everyday 1-2 participant children were examined along with interview of the respondents. The data were collected till the end of study period was reached. History was collected from the parents of each child under study. It

was noted in the schedule. General and systemic examinations of every participating child were done. Prescriptions from registered medical practitioners, past

medical records or discharge certificates from hospitals were scrutinized before confirming past or present illness.

significance 0.05 (5%) i. e. $p < 0.05$ was considered to be significant.

V. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The collected data were entered into Microsoft excel (2010) application software package and checked for any entry error. Few tests were also performed in SPSS. Frequency distribution, descriptive statistics, percentage, chi- squared test were applied to analyze the data. To know the significance of the test statistics we apply the level of

VI. RESULTS

A total of 220 children(110 -single child, 110- child with siblings) were included in our study. Scores were calculated according to the questionnaire of the Modified Child Behaviour checklist and were categorized into Good , Average and Poor behaviour. The results were as follows:

BEHAVIOUR PATTERN	NO CHILDREN FAMILY		
	SINGLE CHILD	CHILD WITH SIBLING	
GOOD(0-54)	23	97	120
AVERAGE(55-77)	79	13	92
POOR(78-100)	8	0	8
Total	110	110	220

Table no. 1.0 Distribution of behaviour of children

Fig. 1: Distribution of behaviour of children

The above Tab No.1.0 & Fig. No 1.0, show that the Maximum number of single child have Average behavioural pattern , 79 (71.81%) and maximum number of child with siblings have Good behavioural pattern, 97(88.18%) and Minimum number of single child have Poor behavioural pattern 8(7.27%).

Chi square = 43.73, *d. f.* = 2, *p* value =0.001, Significant.

Chi Square test was applied to test the significance of association between single ad sibling child and behavioural patterns of children .The test result shows the value of Chi square = 100.98, which is greater than Chi Square value at 5% level of significance for 2 degree of freedom which

implied there s significant association between the single child, sibling child and behavioural pattern of children.

VII. DISCUSSION

In our study we got maximum number of single child about 71.81% were found to have average behaviour pattern whereas maximum number of child with siblings about 88.18% had good behaviour pattern.

In earlier studies , it has been suggested that being only child could interfere in the intellectual development, in the personality and in the adaptation to social life.(Jiang,1995; Amin, 1998; Lawson & Mace,2009)^{[11][12][13]}.

According to reports only-children receive excessive attention, become selfish, demand a lot of attention, dependent and moody, in comparison to children with siblings (Tavares, Fuchs F.C, Diligenti, Abreu, Rohde & Fuchs, S.C.2004)^[14]

Children may directly learn from siblings the feeling of love and affection towards each other. Siblings may teach social, emotional, language and cognitive assets to other siblings. (Azmitia & Hesser, 1993; Bowes, Maughan, Caspi, Moffitt & Arseneault, 2010; Brody, 2004; Gass, Jenkins & Dunn, 2007)^{[15][16][17][18]}.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Childhood is the most important phase in the life of an individual and the environment in which children are raised plays a big part in the social and personal development. During this period, the child undergoes a remarkable change in life. The patterns of behaviour displayed by children are important indications of their growth and development. Thus it needs a very careful evaluation of the way the child behaves and interacts with others in various situations. Siblings help a lot in shaping the behaviour pattern of a child.

It is the responsibility of the parents and school teachers to understand the child's problem and solve them. Most children without sibling have poor interpersonal skills. The parents must realize this problem and thus guide the children to lead their lives in a healthy manner both physically and mentally.

Every child behaves differently and thus their behavioural qualities should be assessed. Parents should spend as much time as possible with their children irrespective of their profession which will help to reduce the behavioural problem and help to improve the quality of life among single child. Parents can help their children in shaping their behavior and improve the quality of behavior so that when they reach adulthood they will be capable enough to be responsible citizens in the society.

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